

XIAP pulldown with type I and type II receptors.

XIAP is known to bind to RIPK2. It is possible it might also bind to the type I and type II receptors of the BMP and TGF β signalling families. This was tested in vitro using a GST affinity pulldown.

XIAP-c001 – MW: 42267.4 (14059.7 no tag). GST tagged.

MHHHHHSSMSPILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLEYLEEKYEEHLYERDEGDKWRNKKFELGLEFPNLPYYIDGDVKLTQSMAIIRYIADKHN
MLGGCPKERAIEISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSRIAYSKDFETLKVDFLSKLPPEMLKMFEDRLCHKTYLNGDHVTHPDFMLYDALDVVLYMDP
MCLDAFPKLVCFKKRIEAIQIDKYLKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHPPKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMRDHFALDRPSETHADYLLRT
GQVVDISDTIYPRNPAMYSEEARLKSFQNWPDYAHLTPRELASAGLYYTGIGDQVQCFCGGKLNWEPCDRAWSEHRRHFPCFF
VLGRNLNIRSESD

Bait proteins (Alk2, ACVR2, BMPR2, Alk5, TGFBR2) were diluted to between 30 - 50 μ M. Samples were divided into 2 x 200 μ l aliquots. One aliquot was treated with 1mM ATP, 1mM Mg $^{2+}$ to phosphorylate samples. RIPK2 phosphorylated was used as a positive control.

Method

XIAP (GST tagged) was passed over 100ul pre-equilibrated GST resin and washed with 0.5ml binding buffer (500mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 50mM HEPES pH7.5)

200ul of bait protein (Alk2, ACVR2, BMPR2, Alk5, TGFBR2 or RIPK2) was then passed over the resin and the flow through collected.

The resin was then washed with 4 x 1 ml washes with binding buffer.

The XIAP and associated proteins were then eluted with 250ul binding buffer + 10mM reduced glutathione.

Samples of flow through, each wash and the elution were collected separately and gel samples made up using 5ul loading dye + 15ul sample.

Gels were run at 170V for 50 minutes before developing in coomassie instant blue stain.

Samples the elution were also taken for mass spec intact analysis however results not yet available due to a Mass Spec machine pump error that prevented the run.

Gel results shown below:

SDS-PAGE gel results for pull-down. Each protein has lanes 1 – 6.

1 = flow through of bait. 2 = wash 1. 3 = wash 2. 4 = wash 3. 5 = wash 4. 6 = Elution.

- ACVR2 and TGFBR2 show association and are pulled down with XIAP.
- Alk2 (39KDa), BMPR2 (40KDa) and Alk5 Phosphorylated (39KDa) are unclear due to being too close in mass to XIAP (41KDa) to distinguish.
- No association seen with un-phosphorylated Alk5.
- RIPK2 positive control worked. Nul control showed no other contaminants.
- Some degradation of XIAP-GST observed.